

Underwater GPS for Marine ROV

(GPS Bawah Air untuk ROV Marin)

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ABSTRACT

Remotely Operated Vehicle (ROV) is an unoccupied high maneuverable underwater robot that has been widely used in various fields especially in marine research and exploration. ROVs are required to operate within a large area and at depths of several hundred meters underwater, thus, an underwater Global Positioning System (GPS) is necessary for localization, navigation and to aid recovery. However, conventional GPS cannot be used underwater due to poor penetration of short-wave radio frequency. Hence, underwater GPS based on the acoustic signal is proposed. The basic components for an underwater GPS consist of hydrophones, a signal transmitter, and a conventional GPS receiver. Nevertheless, the cost of a hydrophone is extremely high in the market and there is no standard algorithm provided for the underwater GPS. Here we describe the development of an underwater GPS based on the concept of GIB (GPS Intelligent of Buoys) system. The system consists of a low-cost hydrophone and hardware for the underwater GPS that were developed successfully, along with four standard algorithms based on Arduino UNO and MATLAB R2019a. The developed underwater GPS has been tested both over air and underwater. The experimental results show the system performs well which the acoustic signal was successfully generated as periodically, the result for received signal's observation and TOA obtained was acceptable. In consequence, the developed underwater GPS can aid activities such as real-time monitoring, geotagging, and mapping, besides improving the ROV's overall performance.

Keywords: Underwater GPS, Intelligent of Buoys (GIB), Time of Arrival (TOA), Hydrophone, Arduino UNO

ABSTRAK

ROV (Remotely Operated Vehicle) merupakan sebuah robot bawah air tanpa penumpang dan mempunyai kemampuan kawalan pergerakan yang tinggi. ROV telah banyak digunakan dalam pelbagai bidang khususnya dalam bidang pendidikan untuk mengeksploitasi laut. Biasanya, ROV harus menjalankan tugasannya dalam kedalaman beratus-ratus malahan beribu-ribu meter di bawah paras laut. Jadi, sistem kedudukan sejagat (GPS) amat memerlukan supaya memudahkan kawalannya dan mengelakkan kehilangan ROV. Namun, GPS konvensional tidak dapat digunakan dalam air kerana kelemahan pemancaran isyarat berfrekuensi radio di dalam air. Dengan ini, sistem GPS bawah air berdasarkan konsep gelombang akustik dicadangkan. Komponen-komponen asas untuk sebuah GPS bawah air termasuklah hidrofون, pendering dan penerima GPS konvensional tetapi harga hidrofون dalam pasaran amat mahal dan tiada algoritma piawai untuk GPS bawah air. Dengan ini, dalam jurnal ini, kita menerangkan perkembangan sebuah GPS bawah air yang berdasarkan konsep sistem GIB (GPS Intelligent of Buoys). GPS bawah air yang merangkumi hidrofون dan perkakasan yang berkos rendah telah berjaya dibangunkan dengan empat algoritma piawai yang dibangunkan melalui perisian Arduino UNO dan MATLAB R2019a. GPS bawah air yang telah dibangunkan telah diuji kaji melalui medium udara dan air serta keputusan uji kaji menunjukkannya berfungsi dengan bagus di mana isyarat akustik telah berjaya dijanakan secara berkala dan keputusan pemerhatian isyarat yang diterima serta TOA yang diperolehi adalah memuaskan. Pendek kata, GPS bawah air yang dibangunkan bukan sahaja dapat memudahkan kegiatan seperti pemantauan nyata masa, geo-tagging dan lain-lain malahan dapat meningkatkan prestasi ROV.

Kata Kunci: GPS Bawah Air; Intelligent of Buoys (GIB); Masa ketibaan (TOA); Hidrofون, Arduino UNO

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, there have been rapid progress in the development of ROVs (Remotely Operated Vehicles), which have played an important role in a

variety of application fields of marine research and exploration. According to (NOAA 2014), ROV is an unoccupied, highly maneuverable underwater robot that is remotely connected by cable and controlled by an operator. It cannot be denied that ROVs have

important usage in many different fields such as education, science and innovation, military, etc. However, ROVs are becoming more popularly used in marine research by scientists for collecting data and monitoring purposes. For example, the researchers from MBARI (Monterey Bay Aquarium Research Institute) used their ROV to monitor lifeforms under 900 meters sea level and collect parametric data such as oxygen consumption by the underwater organisms in order for investigating the effect of climate change towards the marine life (Greenemeier 2009).

Typically, ROVs are required to perform their task such as monitoring, collecting data, searching landmine, and so on underwater at depths up to several hundreds, sometimes even thousands, meters. Therefore, it is necessary to have the ROVs equipped with Global Positioning System (GPS) to aid navigation and recovery of lost ROVs. Besides, ROVs which equipped with GPS can be used for geotagging. Nevertheless, conventional GPS could not be used effectively in deep water due to the poor penetration of electromagnetic signal. The electromagnetic signal will be attenuated in the water and causes the conventional GPS receiver to not function well in water (Christ & Wernli 2013; Taraldsen et al. 2011). Hence, acoustic sound wave becomes a popular alternative as data carrier for an underwater GPS system.

There are three classical acoustic positioning systems for underwater GPS, which are Ultra Short Baseline System (USBL), Short Baseline System (SBL) and Long Baseline System (LBL). These three classical acoustic positioning systems are classified based on the concept of baseline. The concept of the baseline can be defined as the distance between the active sensors (Béchéaz & Thomas 2002; Christ & Wernli 2013; Pisa et al. 2007). Besides these classical positioning systems, a modern acoustic positioning system called GPS Intelligent of Buoys (GIB) has been developed by ACSA (Advanced Concept and System Architecture) in 1996. GIB system is an acoustic positioning system that consists of buoys equipped with GPS receivers and hydrophone and it was designed to detect the location of the target that is equipped with an acoustic signal transmitter. The

relative distance between the target and the hydrophone can be estimated by using the TOA (Time of Arrival) of the acoustic signal. Next, the exact location of the target is obtained by combining the relative distance with the location of the buoys equipped with GPS receiver (Alcocer et al. 2006; Pisa et al. 2007).

The main components of an underwater GPS include acoustic signal transmitter, hydrophone, and conventional GPS receiver. However, the market price for a hydrophone is extremely high which has burdened the researchers. Besides, there has been no standard algorithm for the underwater GPS operation. Thus, in this paper we describe the development of an underwater GPS based on the concept of the GIB system with low-cost hydrophones and hardware. Furthermore, we also aim to develop a standard algorithm for underwater GPS. The development of the system has been divided into five parts, which are hydrophone development, electrical hardware development, acoustic signal generation, testing, and signal analysis.

Therefore, in this paper, we present the system objectives that are the development of hydrophones and hardware for the underwater GPS, testing of the developed underwater GPS, and finally, the observation and discussion based on the testing result.

In the system, an Arduino UNO development microcontroller board was programmed to generate a specific acoustic signal and obtain TOA. Additionally, the algorithm for the underwater GPS also developed through the platform of Arduino UNO and MATLAB R2019a.

METHODOLOGY

As discussed before, the development of the system has been divided into five parts which are hydrophone development, electrical hardware development, acoustic signal generation, testing, and signal analyzation in order to achieve the objectives of the project. Thus, this development was carried out by according to the flow chart as shown in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: Flow diagram for the project.

Besides, Figure 2 shows the block diagram for the developed underwater GPS. The block diagram illustrates the relationship between the electronic components and the flow of operation of the developed underwater GPS. As shown in Figure 2, there are two main circuits for the developed

underwater GPS which have been named as Circuit I and Circuit II. Circuit I consists of an acoustic signal transmitter, hydrophone, and an audio amplifier, MAX 9814 module whereas Circuit II consists of a conventional GPS receiver, NEO-6M module.

FIGURE 2: Block diagram of developed underwater GPS.

Hydrophone Development

To achieve one of the objectives of this project which is developing a low-cost hydrophone, research on hydrophone development has been carried out at the earlier stage of the project. In this project, the design of the hydrophone was adapted and modified from (Joy et al. 2012).

The required components to build up a hydrophone are piezoelectric elements, hydrophone holder, audio amplifier, waterproof material, and stranded wire.

Piezoelectric elements have been used to build up the hydrophone because they can convert the mechanical stress due to sound waves into electrical signals. There are various sizes and types of piezoelectric elements available in the market

(APC International Ltd 2012). In this project, a piezo disc with a diameter of 35 mm has been used since the greater the surface, the higher the probability to receive acoustic signals. Then, the epoxy resin has been used as a waterproof material to waterproof the piezoelectric element and wiring in the hydrophone holder. The epoxy resin was chosen due to its electric conductivity and high moisture resistance compared to the traditional thermoset (Johnson 2019). PVC (polyvinyl chloride) socket was used as a hydrophone holder due to its tough characteristics.

Based on (Joy et al. 2012), the wire of the piezoelectric element has been substituted by longer stranded wire. Next, the piezoelectric element was placed into the PVC socket and the epoxy resin was poured into the PVC socket. Moreover, the surface of the piezoelectric element was coated with a thin layer of epoxy resin. The developed hydrophone will be shown in the Result.

Electrical Hardware Development

The electrical hardware development for an underwater GPS consists of two main circuits as discussed before. By referring to Figure 2, Circuit I consists of a hydrophone, acoustic signal generation, and audio amplifier whereas Circuit II consists of a conventional GPS receiver.

In this project, Arduino UNO boards were used in both Circuit I and Circuit II as a microcontroller. Arduino UNO has been programmed to carry out specific tasks such as generate an acoustic signal and transmit it through an acoustic signal transmitter, convert received acoustic signal which in analog form into digital form, obtain the TOA, and decoding the NMEA sentences.

Besides, since the amplitude of the received acoustic signal is low, an audio amplifier is required to amplify the received acoustic signal. MAX 9814 module was used because it has auto amplification and bias functions. It has 3 amplification selection and in this project, the signal was amplified by 60 dB (Maxim Integrated 2009). Additionally, the NEO-6M module, a conventional GPS receiver was used due to its popularity whereas buzzer was used as an acoustic signal transmitter (AREENDRAN 2019; blox 2017).

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the connection of the electronic components with the Arduino UNO board of Circuit I and Circuit II respectively.

FIGURE 3: Set up for Circuit I.

FIGURE 4: Set up for Circuit II.

Acoustic Signal Generation

In this project, acoustic signal generation was done by *Tone* which is a built-in function in Arduino UNO. By using the *Tone* function, the acoustic signal can be generated in frequency in the range of 31 Hz to 65535 Hz. Since the suitable frequency of the acoustic signal that can be transmitted the water is between 10 Hz to 1 MHz, hence, six acoustic signals with the frequencies of 31 Hz, 50 Hz, 1000 Hz, 5000 Hz, 10000 Hz, and 65535 Hz were chosen and generated. The generated periodic acoustic signal is then transmitted by buzzer periodically.

Algorithm Development

There are four algorithms that were developed through the platform of Arduino UNO and MATLAB R2019a. These four algorithms were named as Algorithm SISTEM_GIB, Algorithm GPS_NMEA, Algorithm TINYGPS, and Algorithm SIGNAL.

These four algorithms are used to carry out specific tasks such as acoustic signal generation, obtain TOA, observe a received signal, etc. More discussion of these algorithms is made in the Results.

Testing

Once the underwater GPS was built up, the developed underwater GPS was tested both over air and underwater.

For the testing over the air, the testing was carried out in a quiet room. The buzzer and hydrophone were placed apart by a longitudinal tube with a length of 1.13m. The tube was used to enhance sound propagation. Then, the received signal was observed through MATLAB R2019a in real-time.

For the underwater testing, it could be assigned into two parts. First, the system was tested using a bucket of 0.0185 m³ (radius = 0.14m and depth = 0.3 m). The hydrophone was placed on the water and faced downwards whereas the buzzer was placed in the water. The real-time monitoring of the received signal also has been carried out through MATLAB R2019a. Then, the second part of the testing underwater is planning to be carried out in an Olympic standard swimming pool. However, due to MCO (Malaysia Control Order), the testing couldn't be carried out.

Signal Analysis

Other than real-time monitoring of the received signal in the time domain, the received signal also has been analyzed in the frequency domain through MATLAB R019a. To analyze the received signal in the frequency domain, STFT (Short Time Fourier Transform) was used. A spectrogram is a visual representation result of STFT. The y-axis of the spectrogram is the frequency of the sound, the x-axis is the time or the number of samples whereas the amplitude of the signal is represented by the colour intensity.

Target's Location

Figure 5 shows the working principle of the underwater GPS based on the concept of the GIB system. The buoys or ship is equipped with a conventional GPS receiver to obtain the physical location of the target. Furthermore, the buoys also equipped with hydrophones whereas the marine ROV (target) is equipped with an acoustic signal transmitter. The TOA of the acoustic signal is used to calculate the relative distance between the hydrophones and the target.

FIGURE 5: Working principle of underwater GPS based on the concept of the GIB system.

The information obtained by the conventional GPS receiver, NEO-6M is in the form of NMEA (National Marine Electronics Association) where NMEA 1083 was developed to provide a user-friendly approach to mix and match the hardware and devices (Gakstatter 2015). Since the user required to take some time to read and extract specific parameters from the NMEA sentences, thus, the Arduino UNO board was programmed to decode the NMEA sentences using the built-in library, *TinyGPS++.h*. This could easier the user obtain pieces of information that they interested such as latitude, longitude, time, etc.

Next, to obtain relative distance, TOA is the most important factor. TOA is the flight time of the signal from an acoustic signal transmitter to the hydrophone. Equation (1) illustrates the relationship between TOA with the signal received time and transmitted time.

$$TOA = \text{Received Time} - \text{Transmitted Time} \quad (1)$$

Here, TOA was obtained by programmed the Arduino UNO board. The transmitted time is defined as the time of each generated signal being transmitted whereas the received time is defined as the time once the threshold value (the peak of the acoustic signal) is detected. Hence, the threshold value of the received signal was observed using Serial Plotter of the Arduino UNO. Then, the setting of the threshold value in the developed algorithm has been changed according to the observation and run again the algorithm. Next, the TOA was calculated by Arduino UNO based on Equation (1) using the recorded received time and transmitted time.

The speed of sound in the water also very important in obtaining the relative distance. The speed of sound in the water is varied by the factor such as temperature, salinity, and depth. Equation Del Grosso (Christ & Wernli 2013; Sgorbini et al. 2002) as shown in Equation (2) illustrates the relationships between the speed of sounds, c with these parameters where T is the temperature of the water (°C), S is the salinity (PSU) and D is the depth (m).

$$c = 1448.6 + 4.618T - 0.0523T^2 + 1.25(S - 35) + 0.017D \quad (2)$$

Once the TOA and speed of sound in the water have been obtained, the relative distance can be calculated. There are two calculations which are calculation when only one hydrophone is used and calculation when at least 3 hydrophones are used.

When only 1 hydrophone is used during the operation, the relative distance is obtained by using Equation (3) where relative distance, r is the product of the speed of sound in the water, c , and TOA.

$$r = c \times \text{TOA} \quad (3)$$

When more than three hydrophones are used, an instantaneous positioning algorithm is used. In this paper, the developed underwater GPS only compatible with 1 hydrophone.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hydrophone and Electrical Hardware

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show the hydrophone and hardware that have been developed for the underwater GPS system. The total cost to build a hydrophone for this project is as low as RM 200 which is much lower compared to other hydrophones on the market. For example, the hydrophone that manufactured by DolpinEar is costed at around \$319. Based on Figure 7, there are two circuits were developed for underwater GPS as discussed before.

FIGURE 6: Developed hydrophones. (a) Front view. (b) Side view. (c) Back view.

(a) Circuit for conventional GPS receiver (Circuit II).

(b) Circuit for buzzer, hydrophone and MAX 9814 (Circuit I).

FIGURE 7: Set up for underwater GPS. (a) Circuit I. (b)Circuit II.

Developed Algorithm

A total of four algorithms were developed through the platform of Arduino UNO and MATLAB R2019a. These four algorithms are used to carry out specific tasks for the underwater GPS. Table 1 shows the functions of each developed algorithms.

TABLE 1: Function for each algorithm.

Algorithms	Functions
Algorithm SYSTEM_GIB	a. Generate a specific acoustic signal. b. Transmit the generated signal through the buzzer. c. Real-time monitoring of the generated acoustic signal. d. Real-time monitoring of the received signal. e. Obtain TOA.
Algorithm GPS NMEA	Obtain information from the NEO-6M module in the format of NMEA.
Algorithm TINYGPS	Decode the NMEA sentences.
Algorithm SIGNAL	a. Real-time monitoring of the received signal in the time domain or frequency domain (STFT).

Testing Over the Air

Few interferences have been observed when the developed underwater GPS was testing over the air due to the processes of signal generation and the signal reception was conducted by using the same Arduino UNO board. Therefore, the observation of interference has been conducted in 3 conditions as shown in Table 2 whereas Figure 8 shows the observations of the interferences for these conditions respectively. All observations shown in this paper is

based on the acoustic signal of 1000 Hz.

To observe the interferences, the Algorithm SYSTEM_GIB was used and the reading of the signal was carried out on the A0 pin of the Arduino UNO board throughout these three situations. Based on Figure 8(a), the observation of the received signal in Situation 1 shows the occurring of random numbers on the A0 pin which was caused by the ambient electric noise. Moreover, Figure 8 (b) shows that interference has occurred when the piece of an algorithm for signal generation and reception in Algorithm SYSTEM_GIB were activated at the same time but there is no sensors were connected to the board. Figure 8(c) shows the different interference waveform when the piece of the algorithm for signal generation and reception was activated but only the buzzer was connected to the Arduino board and the A0 pin was floated. Thus, based on these observations, we can conclude that the interference occurred due to the process of signal generation and reception are carried out on the same Arduino UNO board instead of caused by the limitation of the Arduino UNO board.

(a) Reading on the A0 pin (Situation 1).

(b) Reading on the A0 pin (Situation 2).

(c) Reading on the A0 pin (Situation 3).

FIGURE 8: Observation of interferences. (a) Situation 1. (b) Situation 2. (c) Situation 3.

TABLE 2: Set up for interference observation.

Settings/ Conditions	1	2	3
a. Obtain reading from the A0 pin of the Arduino UNO board.	√	√	√
b. Buzzer connected to the Arduino UNO board.	X	X	√
c. Hydrophone and MAX 9814 module are connected to Arduino UNO.	X	X	X
d. The algorithm for acoustic signal generation is activated.	X	√	√
e. The algorithm for signal reception/ Algorithm for reading on the A0 pin is activated.	√	√	√

Other than observation of interferences, the observation of the generated acoustic signal and the received acoustic signal over the air were also conducted. The observations are shown in Figure 9. By comparing Figure 9(a) and Figure 9(b), we observed that the amplitude of the received acoustic signal (319) is lower than the generated acoustic signal (362). This phenomenon occurred due to the loss of signal energy during the sound propagation.

From the other sides of the coin, the amplitude of the generated acoustic signal was affected by the interference since the amplitude of the waveform due to the interference for situation 2 and situation 3 were 280 and 321 respectively whereas the amplitude of the generated signal was 362. This shows that the amplitude of the generated acoustic signal was much higher due to the interference.

FIGURE 9: Observation when testing conducted over the air. (a) Generated acoustic signal. (b) Received acoustic signal.

Testing Underwater

The testing underwater was carried out using a bucket with 0.0185 m^3 . Due to the pandemic, the original plan which experimented with an Olympic Saiz pool can't be conducted. Figure 10 shows the observation of the received acoustic signal for the testing underwater.

Based on Figure 10, the amplitude of the received acoustic signal in the water (311) is lower than the received acoustic signal over the air (319). This condition occurred due to the amplitude of the acoustic signal was attenuated in the water.

Furthermore, the reduction of the acoustic signal's amplitude or energy is due to the sound absorption in the water. The acoustic signal will be absorbed by the molecules in the water. The

molecules convert the energy from the acoustic signal into heat energy since the propagation of the acoustic signal causes these molecules to vibrate for the sound propagation. Since at the initial, these molecules are at rest before the acoustic signal transmitted in the water, thus, the molecules required to obtain the energy from the acoustic signal to overcome the viscosity of the water and hence cause the amplitude of the acoustic signal reduced (DOSITS n.d.).

FIGURE 10: Testing in the water.

Signal Analyzation

As discussed before, the received acoustic signal also has been analyzed in the frequency domain as shown in Figure 11. Based on Figure 11, the frequency of the received acoustic signal was normalized and shown by the y-axis while the number of samples shown by the x-axis. Also, the colour intensity indicates the amplitude of the received signal with the unit of decibel (dB).

According to (Bäckström 2019), we could obtain a few useful pieces of information based on the Spectrogram such as the comb-like horizontal line indicates the fundamental frequency. For example, based on Figure 11(a), the spectrogram obtained during the testing over the air, the comb-like horizontal lines exited when samples, $n = 600, 1200, \text{ and } 1800$. Thus, we can conclude that the signal was received when $n = 600, 1200 \text{ and } 1800$. Besides, the colour intensity indicates the energy of the signal (amplitude). Hence, based on Figure 11(a), the signal energy at $n = 600, 1200 \text{ and } 1800$ was around 50 dB. With this in mind, the spectrogram for the testing underwater which is shown in Figure 11(b) can be interpreted in the same way.

(a) Testing over the air.

(b) Testing underwater.

FIGURE 11: Spectrogram. (a) Testing over the air. (b) Testing underwater.

TOA

Figure 12 shows the comparison between the TOA obtained over the air and underwater for each frequency of the acoustic signal at a distance of 1.13m.

Based on Figure 12, TOA for the signal with frequency 1000 Hz and below were similar and constant. This phenomenon can be explained by using Equation (4).

$$f = \frac{r}{TOA \times \lambda} \quad (4)$$

FIGURE 12: Comparisons between TOA that obtained through both the testing over the air and underwater.

Since the testing was carried out over the air and with the same distance of 1.13 m, thus, the speed of sound and distance was constant. Therefore, when the frequency of the acoustic signal increased, the wavelength of the signal is decreased at the same time, so, TOA remains constant. Nevertheless, the TOA for the signal with 5000 Hz and above when the test conducted over the air is shorter than the acoustic signal with frequency 1000 Hz and below. This condition was caused by the waveform of the

generated acoustic signal. The signal with frequency 5000 Hz and above have sharper waveform compared with the acoustic signal which has frequency 1000 Hz and below as shown in Figure 13.

Thus, for the acoustic signal of 1000 Hz and below, the TOA which recorded based on the threshold value of the acoustic signal may have some delay.

(a) Acoustic signal of 50 Hz.

(b) Acoustic signal of 65535 Hz.

FIGURE 13: Waveform of the acoustic signal. (a) 50 Hz. (b) 65535 Hz.

While for the TOA obtained during the testing underwater, the TOA for each signal is not constant. This condition was caused by the environmental restriction. The experiment was carried out using a bucket that has a small volume and results in some problems such as sound reflection. Besides, the speed of sound in the water is affected by the salinity, temperature, and depth as discussed before and it causes the multipath and refraction of sound. Thus, these phenomena would affect the TOA obtained during the testing underwater.

As the prospect of the result of TOA for the testing underwater, the TOA obtained should be shorter than the TOA when the testing carried out over the air since the propagation of sound in pure water (1440 m/s) or seawater (1560 m/s) is faster

than air (343 m/s) (Christ & Wernli 2013).

Target's Location

NEO-6M module was used to obtain the physical location of the target. As we all known, the information obtained by NEO-6M was printed in the format of NMEA as shown in Figure 14.

Then, the algorithm has been modified to decode the NMEA sentences as shown in Figure 15. Figure 15 shows the NMEA sentences were decoded and only the interested parameter such as latitude and longitude were printed. Based on Figure 15, the physical location of the target is (1.660991, 103.588432).

```

10:13:55.254 -> $GPGSV,3,1,09,01,63,080,28,07,49,345,44,08,13,025,19,09,45,227,25*71
10:13:55.326 -> $GPGSV,3,2,09,11,43,029,37,16,00,080,,17,29,252,21,30,20,331,22*7D
10:13:55.399 -> $GPGSV,3,3,09,50,63,093,37*4E
10:13:55.429 -> $GPGLL,0139.73169,N,10335.29156,E,021355.00,A,D*60
10:13:55.996 -> $GPRMC,021356.00,A,0139.73167,N,10335.29155,E,0.096,,140620,,D*79
10:13:56.066 -> $GFWTGT,,T,,M,0.096,N,0.178,K,D*27
10:13:56.102 -> $GPRGA,021356.00,0139.73167,N,10335.29155,E,2,08,2.06,30.6,M,4.4,M,,0000*54
10:13:56.174 -> $GPGSA,A,3,01,50,07,09,17,11,30,08,,,,,4.89,2.06,4.43*07
10:13:56.246 -> $GPGSV,3,1,09,01,63,080,28,07,49,345,44,08,13,025,19,09,45,227,27*73
10:13:56.318 -> $GPGSV,3,2,09,11,43,029,37,16,00,080,,17,29,252,21,30,20,331,22*7D
    
```

FIGURE 14: Information printed in the format of NMEA.

```

10:15:57.261 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:15:59.181 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:00.072 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:00.180 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:01.076 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:01.182 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:02.070 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:02.178 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:03.075 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
10:16:03.178 -> Latitude = 1.662244 Longitude = 103.588218
    
```

FIGURE 15: The NMEA sentences decoded and only interested parameters were printed.

Then, the obtained physical location is inserted into Google Maps in order to obtain the accuracy of the NEO-6M module as shown in Figure 16. Based on Figure 16, the differences between the location obtained by Google Maps and the location obtained from NEO-6M are 0m. This shows the accuracy of NEO-6M is very high.

FIGURE 16: Comparison between NEO-6M modul with Google map.

Besides, to obtain the exact location of the target based on the concept of the GIB system, the relative distance is combined with the physical location of the target. However, due to the pandemic, the experiment which plans to conduct in an Olympic size pool in order to determine the relative distance is not able to be carried out.

CONCLUSION

The prototype for underwater GPS with low-cost hydrophones and hardware based on the concept of the GIB system was successfully developed. Four algorithms have been developed through the platform of Arduino UNO and MATLAB R2019a to perform specific task such as generate acoustic

signal, observe received or generated signal, obtain TOA, obtain physical location of the target whether in NMEA form or decoded form and last but not least, analysis the received signal using STFT. The developed underwater GPS is small in size, portable, and easy to be used and installed. The testing result shows the prototype performs well and last but not least, the objectives for this project have been achieved and hope the developed underwater GPS could benefit the coming generations.

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